

Potential effect of listeriolysin O toxin on the 5-Fluorouracil cytotoxic effects in MCF-7 cell line

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Abstract

Objective: Cholesterol-dependent cytolysins are a class of pore-forming toxins with the largest pores create in the target cell membranes. One of the best-studied toxins in this family, listeriolysin O, act only in the acidic pH of endosomes. One mutant of this toxin (E247M/D320K) has shown to be active and stable in the physiological pH (7.4). In the present study, we have explored the differential potentiation effect of the wild-type and mutant listeriolysin O on the cytotoxic effects of the chemotherapeutic agent 5-Fluorouracil in MCF-7 cell line as a model.

Material and Method: Both toxins were produced as a recombinant His-tagged form in *E. coli* and purified using nickel-affinity chromatography. Hemolytic activity and pH-stability of the recombinant wild-type and E247M/D320K mutant listeriolysin O toxins were assessed using hemolysis assay on human RBCs. Cytotoxic effect of the 5-Fluorouracil chemotherapeutic agent was analyzed in the presence and absence of non-toxic concentrations of the recombinant toxins.

Results: Results showed that the mutations introduced in the listeriolysin O molecule for its physiological pH stability decreased its bioactivity by a factor of about 4. Potentiation effects of the wild-type listeriolysin O and its mutant were in acidic and neutral pH respectively.

Conclusion: We concluded that this mutant of listeriolysin O could be a choice in the therapeutic applications of the toxin where the physiological pH of 7.4 is using. Direct introduction of chemotherapeutics across the membrane (rather than the endosomal compartments) would be much more helpful in the potentiation of cancer chemotherapeutic agents' effects.

Keywords: Chemotherapy, Listeriolysin O, MCF-7 Cells, Potentiation, Toxin.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chemotherapy as the most common type of cancer treatment strategy removes cancer cells by inhibiting the growth of cancer cells and cell division [1].

Despite the wide range of chemotherapy applications, its complications still remained including resistance of cancer cells and death of healthy fast-growing cells [2].

Several strategies are used to overcome chemotherapy resistance, including: the use of new anti-cancer drugs [3], MDR (Multiple drug Resistance) modulators or chemosensitizers [4], multifunctional Nano carriers [5], and biological treatments like RNA interference (RNAi)[6] and etc. Especially biological and nano-biotechnological advancements have opened new window on cancer therapy.

Nano-carriers (liposomes, nanoparticles) deliver chemical and biological therapeutics much more efficiently to cancer cells [7,8]. Pore-Forming Toxins (PFTs) perturb cell membrane integrity by inserting their monomers into the lipid bilayer and oligomerizing into multi-subunit pores [9].

Research studies have been used pore forming toxins as delivery systemsto transfer antigens [10], antisense oligonucleotides [11], genes [12], chemical drugs [13] to cells by using sub-lethal doses of these toxins.

Listeriolysin O (LLO), possibly the most studied member of the pore-forming toxin superfamily of proteins, has optimum activity in acidic phagosomes and help listeria monocytogenes escape from the acidic endosomes into cytoplasm [14]. So delivery systems based on the listeriolysin O are only active in the acidic microenvironment of acidic endosomes [15,16].

Listeriolysin O belongs to CDC family of pore forming toxins (PFTs). Members of this family form pores in the cell membrane which are distinct in size and structure from other PFTs. The much larger size of the pore allows for larger molecules and complexes to be delivered cell interior [17]. Other protein toxins with the same mechanism of action were also used for delivery of chemotherapeutics.

Sea anemone pore-forming cytolysins, Bc2 and equinatoxin (EqTx-II), were used to sensitize human glioblastoma cells to cytosine arabinoside, doxorubicin, and vincristine [18]. Epsilon toxin produced by *Clostridium perfringens* was used to deliver methotrexate to COR-L105 Human Caucasian lung adenocarcinoma cells and MDA-MB 231 human breast cancer cells [19].

In 2005, mutated recombinant LLO toxin was produced that has a greater structural stability than wild-type LLO in neutral pH [14]. To address the benefits of CDC family members larger pore size and the stability of the new mutant of listeriolysin in physiological pH which may lead to the direct delivery of chemical drugs through listeriolysin O pores into cytoplasm, we have used the mutant listeriolysin O as a delivery system in human breast cancer cells in vitro.

2. MATERIAL AND METOD

Materials

E. coli XL-1 and BL21 (DE3) strains were prepared from Pasteur Institute, Iran, Ni-NTA Agarose from Qiagen, plasmid extraction miniprep and DNA gel recovery kits from Sinaclon Co., Iran. DpnI restriction enzyme was from Thermo Fisher Scientific Co., Taq DNA polymerase master mix from Amplicon, fetal bovine serum from Gibco, MCF-7 cell line from Pasture Institute, Iran and other chemicals used in this project were purchased from Sigma and Merck Co., Germany.

Cloning and site-directed mutagenesis

pPSG-IBA35-LLO expression construct was a gift from Dr. R. Stachowiak [20]. Chemically competent XL-1 Blue *E. coli* cells were prepared using calcium chloride conventional method.

30 nanograms of recombinant expression construct were used to transform competent cells. One of the XL-1 Blue *E. coli* transformants was cultured in 5-ml LB broth medium containing 50 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of ampicillin and incubated overnight at 37°C in a shaker incubator (150 rpm). Recombinant plasmid was extracted with column method (QIAprep Spin Miniprep kit, Qiagen™) for the transformation of BL21 (DE3) competent cells.

To create E247M mutation in listeriolysin O gene, pPSG-IBA35-LLO was used as template in a simple PCR which produced two overlapping fragments of the LLO gene. Fragment 1 was produced with forward primer complementary to the backbone of the vector upstream of the LLO gene, and reverse primer complementary to the LLO gene in the codon 247.

Fragment 2 was created with forward primer complementary to codon 247 and reverse primer complementary to the vector backbone downstream of the gene. Two fragments were connected

to each other by a SOEing PCR to produce the whole insert gene plus two fragments of the vector backbone.

The product of this SOEing PCR was gel purified and used in a quick-change PCR step to synthesize the remaining parts of the pPSG-IBA35 expression vector. Then product of the quick-change step was cleaned up, treated by DpnI and transformed into XL-1 Blue *E. coli* competent cells. Mutant colonies were confirmed with DNA sequencing. All above steps were performed for the second mutation (D230K).

Expression and purification of recombinant toxins

30 nanograms of each recombinant construct were used to transform BL21 (DE3) competent cells which were prepared with the same method. One of BL21 (DE3) transformants was cultured in a 5-mL LB broth medium containing 50 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of ampicillin, at 37°C, and incubated overnight at 37°C in a shaker incubator (150 rpm). A fresh aliquot of this culture was inoculated into a 100-mL of the same medium and was grown at 37°C until an OD_{600nm} ~ 0.7. Culture was then induced with 1 mM IPTG (isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactopyranoside) and incubated overnight at 37°C.

The induced culture was harvested by centrifugation (6,000 x g, 5 min, 4°C) and the resulting cell pellet was suspended in 5 mL of denaturing lysis buffer (Na₂HPO₄, 50 mM, pH=6.0; NaCl, 300 mM; 2ME, 5 mM; glycerol, 10 %). Resuspended bacterial pellet was bead-beated for 20 seconds and 15 times with a bench-top vortex with maximum shaking speed (2000 rpm) with 30 seconds intervals incubating on ice. Soluble fraction was centrifuged and the supernatant was loaded on to an Ni-NTA agarose resin column (Qiagen Inc.). Equilibration and wash buffer were the same as lysis buffer. Elution buffer was also the same as lysis buffer except the 300 mM imidazole. For investigating the presence of recombinant LLO protein, eluted fractions were analyzed by Coomassie Blue-stained 10% SDS-PAGE. Fractions containing purified recombinant protein were dialyzed in dialysis buffer (the same as lysis buffer except of 50 mM NaCl).

Protein concentration determination by Bradford Method:

3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 μg of BSA as standard protein and an aliquot of each sample were mixed with 50 μl of 1 N NaOH and the total volume was reached to 1 ml with Bradford solution. After a 5-minute incubating at room temperature, absorbance of each sample was monitored at 590 nm. Concentration of each sample was obtained using a calibration curve.

Western blot analysis

After loading samples in a 10% SDS-PAGE, samples were transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane. Membrane was washed three times with a TBS buffer (Tris, 20 mM; NaCl, 150 mM;) shaking for 15 minutes, blocked with 10-ml of blocking solution (BSA 5%) for 2 hours, and then was washed 3 times with a TBST buffer (TBS+ Tween 0.05%) for 15 minutes.

8 μl Anti-6XHis Tag antibody was mixed with 4 ml of blocking solution and then poured onto the membrane for 2 hours on the

shaker, and then the membrane was washed with a TBST buffer 3 times for another 15 minutes. The membrane was developed by ECL kit and the result was monitored in a gel doc.

Hemolysis assay

The hemolytic activity of wild-type LLO and mutant LLO were determined with human RBC hemolysis assay. Hemolysis buffer (Na₂HPO₄, 50 mM; 2ME, 10 mM) was prepared in two pH, 5.5 and 7.4. RBC was washed three times with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and resuspended in hemolysis buffer until OD₆₀₀ nm of 1-1.2. For the assay, 10 µl of each toxin was added to 190 µl RBC suspension and absorbance of the sample was measured at 600 nm after 5 minutes of incubation at 37°C.

Percentage of hemolysis of any sample was calculated according to the following formula; $H (\%) = [(A_{max} - A_{test}) / (A_{max} - A_{min})] \times 100$.

For determining the remaining hemolytic activity of toxins in each pH (5.5 and 7.4), a concentration of toxins with approximately 50% of the maximum hemolytic activity was selected. After incubating the toxins at different time intervals (0, 200, 400, 600 and 800 seconds), remaining hemolytic activity was calculated.

Cell culture

MCF-7 cell line was cultured in RPMI-1640 medium containing 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 10 µg/ml penicillin-streptomycin and cultivation was took place in incubator with 37°C temperature and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. When cells reach about 80% confluence, cells were harvested using 0.05% Trypsin-EDTA.

MTT assay

The MTT (3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) tetrazolium reduction assay was used to investigate potentiation effect of 5-fluorouracil in the presence of recombinant toxins on MCF-7 cell line. 104 cells were placed in each well of a 96-well plate and incubated for 24 hours. Cells were treated with recombinant toxins which were diluted in relating phosphate buffer for 45 min. After removing toxins, three concentrations of 5FU (5, 50 and 500 µM) was added and incubated for another 24 hours. The whole culture media was removed from wells and 20 µl MTT reagent (5 mg.ml⁻¹) was added into wells. 100 µl of isopropanol was added into wells and the plates were shaken for 20 minutes, and the absorbance was read at 570 nm.

3. Result

Expression and purification of recombinant toxins

Recombinant wild-type and mutant LLO toxin genes were subcloned in pPSG-IBA35 bacterial expression vector and their expression were induced under the T7 promoter using IPTG. After purification with Ni-NTA resin, as illustrated in (Figur 1), a single band was visible on the SDS-PAGE for eluted fraction of each toxin. Molecular weight of the purified toxins were estimated to be approximately 58 kDa and the purity was calculated to be more than 85%. Western blot analysis confirmed the presence of a his-tagged recombinant protein.

Recombinant protein concentrations were 508 and 544 µg.ml⁻¹ for wild-type and E247M/ D320K mutant respectively (as calculated by Bradford assay). Yield of recombinant productivity were to be approximately 5 mg per liter of BL21 DE3 induced culture media).

Figure1. Purification of recombinant toxins and western blot analysis. (A) SDS-PAGE analysis of purified toxins. Lane 1; purified wild-type listeriolysin O, lane 2; molecular weight size marker of protein, lane 3; purified E247M/ D320K mutant listeriolysin O.

Hemolytic activity of recombinant toxin

Hemolytic activity of each toxin was assessed by hemolysis assay in two pH. EC50 of recombinant wild-type LLO toxin was calculated to be 99.7 and 110.1 ng.ml⁻¹ in pH 5.5 and 7.4 respectively.

EC50 of E247M/D320K mutant LLO toxin was 667.3 and 584.2 ng.ml⁻¹ in the same buffers. As illustrated in (Figure 2), the hemolytic activity of the wild-type toxin was higher at both pH buffers. pH of the hemolysis assay buffer had no effect on the activity of each toxin.

Figure2. Hemolytic activity of recombinant toxins. Dose-response curve of the hemolytic activity of recombinant toxins were illustrated and a sigmoidal fit against the log of concentration was performed to calculate EC₅₀.

For the analysis of the effect of incubating each toxin in buffers with different pH, remaining hemolytic activity of toxins were determined after incubation in related buffers. As shown in (Figure 3), both wild-type and mutant toxins were resistant to

buffer with pH of 5.5, but wild-type listeriolysin O has lost its hemolytic activity by incubating at buffer with pH of 7.4, while the mutant toxin resist this pH.

Figure3. Remaining hemolytic activity of recombinant toxins. Recombinant wild-type and E247M/D320K mutant listeriolysin O toxins were incubated in buffers with pH of 5.5 and 7.4. Remaining hemolytic activity of each toxin has been determined with respect to the un-incubated toxin with the same concentration and has been expressed as percentage.

Morphological changes of MCF-7 cells

To analyze the effects of listeriolysin O on the cytotoxic effects of chemotherapeutic drugs 5FU and methotrexate on MCF-7 cells, non-lethal doses of the recombinant toxins were selected for the assays. Although the concentrations of the toxins were not toxic 24 hours after the 1 hour treatment (0.6 ng/ml and 2.61

ng/ml for wild-type and mutant LLO toxins), but some reversible morphologic changes has been observed according to the (Figure 4). Treated cells has been changed from an epithelial-like morphology to a more spherical shape. But this change was temporary and after 24 hours nearly all cells had their normal epithelial shape.

Figure4. Morphological changes of MCF-7 cells treated by recombinant LLO toxin. MCF-7 cells has epithelial-like morphology (A), which changed to more spherical shape after a 1 hour treatment by recombinant LLO toxin (B), and after 24 hours of incubation in the media free of toxin, the epithelial-like morphology has been reversed without any toxicity (C).

Cytotoxic effects of chemotherapeutic agents

Cytotoxic effects of chemotherapeutic agent, 5-Fluorouracil (5FU), were studied in the presence of non-lethal doses of recombinant listeriolysin O toxins. As shown in (Figure5), results showed that the presence of these non-toxic concentrations of recombinant pore forming toxins has led to the more cytotoxicity of chemotherapeutic agents. In each experiment, three concentration of the chemotherapeutic agent

and two concentration of the recombinant toxin (both concentration were non-toxic) has been applied. For the comparison of the wild-type and E247M/D320K mutant listeriolysin O toxins, two pH of 5.5 and 7.4 has also been compared. As shown in (Figure 5), potentiation effect of wild-type listeriolysin O was more in pH=5.5 than mutant LLO, and the results was the same for this mutant in pH=7.4.

Figure5. Potentiation effect of recombinant listeriolysin O toxins. Cytotoxic effects of 5FU chemotherapeutic agent in the presence of non-toxic concentrations of two recombinant forms of LLO toxins were explored. Wild-type listeriolysin O showed more potentiation effect in acidic pH (5.5) (A), while the E247M/D320K mutant listeriolysin O toxin showed more potentiation effect in neutral pH (7.4).

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Pore forming toxins (PFTs) create pores in the membrane of target cells by oligomerizing in the lipid bilayer. Cholesterol-dependent cytolysins (CDC) comprise one of the largest subfamily of pore-forming toxins which form the largest pores among members of this family of proteins[21]. Pore forming toxins can increase the penetration of macromolecules into target cells by forming pores in the membrane, so the CDC family members with the largest size of pores were potential candidates in this application. Listeriolysin O (LLO) is the major virulence factor implicated in the escape of *Listeria monocytogenes* from the phagolysosomes into cytoplasm of the host cell. Combining listeriolysin O with lipids and the production of toxin-coated liposomes gave new insights to researchers on the delivery of a variety of materials[10,22]. Doxorubicin and bleomycin were co-encapsulated with listeriolysin O in liposomes to be delivered to cancer cells more efficiently[15,16].

The three major acidic residues in the structure of the LLO were identified as a pH-sensor. This pH-sensor is the cause of LLO denaturation and its inactivation in neutral pH [23]. For the activity and stability of listeriolysin O in neutral pH and physiological conditions, the mutations E247M and D320K seems to be inevitable. We aimed in the present study to explore the effect of these mutations in the potentiation effects of listeriolysin O toxin on the cytotoxic effects of 5FU chemotherapeutic agent. If the mutant LLO toxin were able to be more active in this potentiation in physiological pH [7,4], in vivo

application of this toxin would be more feasible. As shown in results, the potentiation effect of E247M/D320K mutant LLO was more at physiologic pH [7,4]. The design of this study made the separated use of LLO toxin and chemotherapeutic agent. We applied the recombinant toxins in the serum-free RPMI 1640 media on the MCF-7 cells for 45 minutes, and after removing this media, we added 5FU drug and incubate the cells for 24 hours. This design would permit the cells to uptake the additional chemotherapeutic agent (5FU) in the presence of recombinant listeriolysin O from the pores in the cytoplasmic membrane. If cells uptake the LLO toxin molecules in the first step of the treatment, there is no chemotherapeutic agent in the endosomes. So the only route for the chemical drug to enter the cells is the pores of the toxin in the cytoplasmic membrane, in addition to the direct passing through the membrane which is identical in all controls and treatments.

CONCLUSION

Chemotherapy drug delivery by listeriolysin O (LLO), as one of the best studied pore-forming toxins, for cancer therapy offers a unique therapeutic approach to overcome chemotherapy resistance in cancer. E247M/D320K mutant version of this pore forming toxin could be a candidate to deliver therapeutic agents in physiological pH.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

5. References

- [1] Chabner BA, Roberts Jr TG. Chemotherapy and the war on cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer* 2005; 5:65.
- [2] Redmond KM, Wilson TR, Johnston PG, Longley DB. Resistance mechanisms to cancer chemotherapy. *Front Biosci* 2008; 13:5138-5154.
- [3] Cragg G, Grothaus P, Newman D. Impact of natural products on developing new anti-cancer agents. *Chemical reviews* 2009; 109:3012-3043.
- [4] Krishna R, Mayer LD. Multidrug resistance (MDR) in cancer: mechanisms, reversal using modulators of MDR and the role of MDR modulators in influencing the pharmacokinetics of anticancer drugs. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2000; 11:265-283.
- [5] Peer D, Karp JM, Hong S, Farokhzad OC, Margalit R, Langer R. Nanocarriers as an emerging platform for cancer therapy. *Nature nanotechnology* 2007; 2:751.
- [6] Nieth C, Priebisch A, Stege A, Lage H. Modulation of the classical multidrug resistance (MDR) phenotype by RNA interference (RNAi). *FEBS letters* 2003; 545:144-150.
- [7] Jurgons R, Seliger C, Hilpert A, Trahms L, Odenbach S, Alexiou C. Drug loaded magnetic nanoparticles for cancer therapy. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* 2006; 18:S2893.
- [8] Sinha R, Kim GJ, Nie S, Shin DM. Nanotechnology in cancer therapeutics: bioconjugated nanoparticles for drug delivery. *Molecular cancer therapeutics* 2006; 5:1909-1917.
- [9] Zelikin AN, Ehrhardt C, Healy AM. Materials and methods for delivery of biological drugs. *Nature chemistry* 2016; 8:997.
- [10] Mandal M, Lee K. Listeriolysin O-liposome-mediated cytosolic delivery of macromolecule antigen in vivo: enhancement of antigen-specific cytotoxic T lymphocyte frequency, activity, and tumor protection. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Biomembranes* 2002; 1563:7-17.
- [11] Andrews CD, Huh M-S, Patton K, Higgins D, Van Nest G, Ott G, et al. Encapsulating immunostimulatory CpG oligonucleotides in listeriolysin O-liposomes promotes a Th1-type response and CTL activity. *Molecular pharmaceutics* 2012; 9:1118-1125.
- [12] Saito G, Amidon G, Lee K. Enhanced cytosolic delivery of plasmid DNA by a sulfhydryl-activatable listeriolysin O/protamine conjugate utilizing cellular reducing potential. *Gene therapy* 2003; 10:72.
- [13] Provoda CJ, Stier EM, Lee K-D. Tumor cell killing enabled by listeriolysin O-liposome-mediated delivery of the protein toxin gelonin. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 2003; 278:35102-35108.
- [14] Schuerch DW, Wilson-Kubalek EM, Tweten RK. Molecular basis of listeriolysin O pH dependence. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 2005; 102:12537-12542.
- [15] Kullberg M, Mann K, Anchordoquy TJ. Targeting Her-2+ breast cancer cells with bleomycin immunoliposomes linked to LLO. *Molecular pharmaceutics* 2012; 9:2000-2008.
- [16] Walls ZF, Gong H, Wilson RJ. Liposomal coencapsulation of doxorubicin with listeriolysin O increases potency via subcellular targeting. *Molecular pharmaceutics* 2016; 13:1185-1190.

- [17] Ruan Y, Rezelj S, Zavec AB, Anderluh G, Scheuring S. Listeriolysin O Membrane Damaging Activity Involves Arc Formation and Lineaction-- Implication for *Listeria monocytogenes* Escape from Phagocytic Vacuole. *PLoS pathogens* 2016; 12:e1005597.
- [18] Soletti RC, de Faria GP, Vernal J, Terenzi H, Anderluh G, Borges HL, et al. Potentiation of anticancer-drug cytotoxicity by sea anemone pore-forming proteins in human glioblastoma cells. *Anti-cancer drugs* 2008; 19:517-525.
- [19] Shekarsaraei AG, Hasannia S, Pirooznia N, Ataiee F. The investigation of epsilon toxin effects on different cancerous cell lines and its synergism effect with methotrexate. *Journal of cancer research and therapeutics* 2014; 10:15.
- [20] Bischofberger M, Iacovache I, Van Der Goot FG. Pathogenic pore-forming proteins: function and host response. *Cell host & microbe* 2012; 12:266-275.
- [21] Tweten RK. Cholesterol-dependent cytolysins, a family of versatile pore-forming toxins. *Infection and immunity* 2005; 73:6199-6209.
- [22] Portnoy DA, Jones S. The cell biology of *Listeria monocytogenes* infection (escape from a vacuole). *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1994; 730:15-25.
- [23] Köster S, Van Pee K, Hudel M, Leustik M, Rhinow D, Kühlbrandt W, et al. Crystal structure of listeriolysin O reveals molecular details of oligomerization and pore formation. *Nature communications* 2014; 5:3690.